

CURING REACTION OF BENZOXAZINE CONTAINING CYANO AND PROPARGYL GROUPS

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1 Introduction

Polybenzoxazine offers an alternative to traditional phenolics, unsaturated polyester resins and epoxies because of its extensive flexibility in molecular design and excellent properties^[1, 2]. The carbon fiber-reinforced polybenzoxazine composites displayed excellent mechanical and thermal properties, even exceeded bismaleimide composites and competed with polyimide composites^[3]. Alkyne groups have been introduced in benzoxazine via molecular design. The acetylene-functional benzoxazines show high thermal stability after cured^[4]. The high thermal stability and high glass transition of polybenzoxazines can also achieve if the molecular structure of benzoxazines was attached by cyano groups. Two kinds of benzoxazines (CP-*p*-appe, CP-*m*-appe) with cyano and propargyl groups were synthesized in this work. By comparison, two benzoxazines (P-*p*-appe, P-*m*-appe) with propargyl

groups were synthesized as well. The curing reactions of the benzoxazines were traced by infrared in situ monitoring to investigate the effect of functional groups and benzoxazine ring on the cross-linking of the benzoxazines. The curing activation energy of the benzoxazine was worked out through thermal analysis and gel time test.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

p-cyanophenol (Kaisai Chemical), paraformaldehyde and 1,4-dioxane (Linfeng Chemical) were used as received. *p*- and *m*-Aminophenyl propargyl ether were prepared from the reaction of *p*- and *m*-aminophenol (Sinopharm Chemical Reagent) and propargyl bromide (Bangcheng Chemical) according to the reported method^[5]. All solvents were chemical pure and used as received.

Scheme 1 Synthetic route of the four Benzoxazines

2.2 Synthesis of four benzoxazines

0.025 mol *p*- or *m*-aminophenyl propargyl ether, 0.025 mol *p*-cyanophenol, 0.05 mol paraformaldehyde and 200 mL 1,4-dioxane were added into a 500 mL four necked round flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a thermometer and a condenser. The reaction was kept at refluxing temperature. The resultant was cooled to room temperature after 5 h and purified by rotary evaporating, dissolving, alkaline and water washing, separating, vacuum drying to obtain brown viscous benzoxazines (CP-*p*-appe and CP-*m*-appe) with cyano and propargyl groups. The synthesis of the benzoxazines (P-*m*-appe and P-*p*-appe) with propargyl group was referred to Ishida and coworkers' processes^[5,6]. A synthetic route of these benzoxazines is shown in Scheme 1.

2.3 Measurements

2.3.1 Infrared in situ monitoring

The viscous benzoxazines were coated on KBr round pellet to form a thin film by a KW-4A spinning machine. The coated KBr pellet was put in the hot cell of Thermo's HT-32 which was programmable to control heating rate. The benzoxazines on the KBr round pellet were non-isothermally polymerized in HT-32 under air atmosphere. FTIR spectra were acquired at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ with 16 coadditions equipped with a deuterated triglycine sulfide (DTGS) detector in the range of room temperature to 355 °C at heating rate of 5 °C/min. The data were collected every 5 min.

2.3.2 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

A benzoxazine sample was put into an aluminum plate, with the weight of about 1 mg. Then the plate was put in the DSC Q2000 measuring chamber under nitrogen atmosphere with the nitrogen flow of 50 mL/min, and run at heating rates of 5 °C/min, 10 °C/min, 20 °C/min, 30 °C/min and 40 °C/min, respectively from room temperature to 350 °C. All benzoxazines were tested in the same way.

2.3.3 Gel time

According to ASTM D3056, the gel time of the four benzoxazines were tested by flat knife method at temperature of 160 °C, 170 °C, 180 °C, 190 °C, and 200 °C, respectively.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Curing behavior of four benzoxazines

The cross-linking of propargyl and cyano-functionalized benzoxazines were examined by DSC (Fig. 1). The results exhibit that there are only one exothermic peak with maximum temperature at 232 °C and 244 °C in P-*p*-appe and P-*m*-appe, respectively. However, the exothermic peaks of CP-*p*-appe and CP-*m*-appe become broad and present shoulder peaks when cyano group incorporated into P-*p*-appe and P-*m*-appe. It implies that introduction of cyano group in the benzoxazines with propargyl groups affect their curing behaviors. The curing reactions of cyano and propargyl groups as well as oxazine ring in the benzoxazines occur simultaneously.

Fig.1. DSC curves of four benzoxazines with functional groups (heating rate: 10 °C/min)

3.2 In situ monitoring of curing reaction of four benzoxazines

Fourier transform infrared can be used to follow those different polymerization reactions simultaneously occurring in the same molecule^[7]. The characteristic peaks of the four benzoxazines are chosen and monitored during curing process. Fig.2 to Fig.5 show FT-IR spectra of P-*p*-appe and CP-*p*-appe at different temperatures. The absorbing peaks at 2222 cm⁻¹ and 2120 cm⁻¹ are attributed to

cyano and alkyne groups, respectively. The absorption bands could be followed and scanned for study on the cross-linking kinetics for the benzoxazines. The results display that both peaks decrease gradually as the reactions proceed. Although the initial thickness of a sample cell is constant, the volume contraction could be arose from occurrence of the curing of the samples, and result in the change of the sample thickness and induce an error between the actual and measured absorbance. The absorption peak at 1613 cm^{-1} which is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ in benzene ring and basically constant, was chosen as the internal standard in order to eliminate the error. The relationship between the conversion ratio and the concentration of monomers can be expressed as:

$$\alpha = (C_0 - C) / C_0 \quad (1)$$

Where C_0 is the initial concentration of the monomers, and C is the concentration of monomers at time t .

Fig.2. FT-IR spectra of P-*p*-appe containing propargyl group at different temperatures

Fig.3. FT-IR spectra of CP-*p*-appe containing cyano and propargyl groups at different temperatures

Fig.4. FT-IR spectra of P-*m*-appe containing propargyl groups at different temperatures

Fig.5. FT-IR spectra of CP-*m*-appe containing cyano and propargyl groups at different temperatures

The absorbance of the reactive groups at different temperatures and times can be measured, and the conversion ratio of cyano and propargyl groups can be calculated. The conversions of cyano and propargyl groups of four benzoxazines versus time are shown in Fig. 6 to Fig. 8. The results show that the conversion of two kinds of functional groups in the benzoxazines arises with increase of curing time. The conversion of propargyl group is much quicker than that of cyano group. The maximum conversion of propargyl groups ranges from about 96% to nearly 100%, and it is larger than that of the cyano groups which have a maximum conversion of 75% in CP-*m*-appe and 66% in CP-*p*-appe at the temperature of 350°C. The conversion of the cyano group increases remarkably while the reaction time ranges from 30 min to 40 min. The corresponding curing temperature ranges from 165°C to 215°C.

Fig. 6. The conversion of propargyl group in P-*p*-appe and P-*m*-appe versus time

Fig. 7. The conversion of cyano and propargyl groups in CP-*p*-appe versus time

While the conversions of propargyl groups are stable and close to 100%, the corresponding reaction temperature is close to 260°C. The conversion of the propargyl in P-*p*-appe is near to that in P-*m*-appe. The effect of cyano group on the conversion of the propargyl in CP-*p*-appe is not obvious. However, the cyano group in CP-*m*-appe influence the conversion of the propargyl group in CP-*m*-appe remarkably. The conversion of propargyl group in CP-*m*-appe is lower than that of propargyl group in P-*m*-appe.

Fig. 8. The conversion of cyano and propargyl groups in CP-*m*-appe versus time

3.3 Calculation of activation energy by DSC

The kinetics analysis in this study following the Kissinger (differential method) and Ozawa (integral) of multiple scanning non-isothermal method, then we can work out the kinetic parameters and make a comparison between them. The advantage of using the two methods is that under the premise of no kinetic model function, and the reliable values of apparent activation energy and frequency factor can be achieved.

The Kissinger function [8] is as follows:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T_p^2}\right) = -\frac{E_a}{RT_p} + \ln\left(\frac{AR}{E_a}\right) \quad (2)$$

While β is linear heating rate, °C/min; T_p , peak temperature, K; E_a , apparent activation energy for the curing reaction, KJ/mol; R , molar gas constant; and A , pre-exponential factor.

And the Ozawa function [9] is as follows:

$$\ln(\beta) = \left(\ln \frac{AE_a}{Rg(a)} \right) - 5.331 - 1.052 \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (3)$$

While $g(a)$ is the integral mechanism function; β , linear heating rate, °C/min; T , thermodynamic temperature; E_a , R and A are the same as above-mentioned. The DSC spectra of P-*p*-appe and CP-*p*-appe at different heating rates are displayed in Fig.9 and Fig.10. The DSC analysis of P-*m*-appe and CP-*m*-appe at different heating rates was implemented as well. According to the peak temperature, the parameters in Kissinger and Ozawa function are given in Table 1 to Table 4.

Fig.9. DSC spectra of P-*p*-appe at different heating rate

Fig.10. DSC spectra of CP-*p*-appe at different heating rate

Kissinger Fitting

Take $\ln(\beta/T_p^2)$ as the ordinate, $1/T_p$ as the abscissa, then make a plotting. The fitting functions are obtained respectively. The linear regression

coefficients R^2 are 0.9400, 0.9785, 0.9691 and 0.9980, respectively. According to the slope, the apparent activation energy E_a of the curing of the benzoxazines are figured out and about 133, 126, 124 and 141 KJ/mol, respectively. Based on the intercept, the frequency factor $\ln A$ are also worked out and are 30.93, 29.12, 28.38, and 31.08, respectively.

Ozawa Fitting

Take $\ln \beta$ as the ordinate, $1/T_p$ as the abscissa. After making a plotting, the fitting functions are got respectively. The linear regression coefficients R^2 are 0.9468, 0.9812, 0.9730 and 0.9983, respectively. And according to the slope, the apparent activation energy E_a are about 135, 128, 126 and 142 KJ/mol, respectively. According to the intercept, the frequency factor $\ln A$ are 31.39, 29.68, 28.99 and 31.51, respectively. The results show that the introduction of cyano group into P-*p*-appe and meta-propargyloxy can decrease E_a , but the introduction of cyano group into P-*m*-appe causes enhancement of E_a . As seen above, with the increasing of heat rate, the peak temperature in DSC curves may shift to the high temperature zone. Kssinger fitting and Ozawa fitting are two wonderful methods to figure out the approximate apparent activation energy and frequency factors of the benzoxazines during cross-linking. And the linear regression coefficients (R^2) are all close to 1. It means that the fitting is feasible.

3.4 Calculation of activation energy by gel time

At the higher temperature, the thermosetting resin reaches its gel points more quickly and its gel time will be shorter^[10]. An Arrhenius model is mostly used to predict the gelation behavior of cross-linking resins^[11-13]. And the Arrhenius function can be written as follows:

$$t_{gel} = A \exp(\Delta E/T) \quad (4)$$

$$\ln t_{gel} = \ln A + (\Delta E/T) \quad (5)$$

where A is a constant, ΔE , an activation energy with

Table 1 Various parameters in linearization fitting (P-*p*-appe)

$\beta/^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$	T_p/K	$(1/T_p)\times 10^{-3}$	$(1/T_p^2)\times 10^{-6}$	$(\beta/T_p^2)\times 10^{-6}$	$\ln(\beta/T_p^2)$	$\ln\beta$
5	502.84	1.9887	3.9549	19.7745	-10.8311	1.6094
10	505.40	1.9786	3.9149	39.1490	-10.1481	2.3026
20	518.41	1.9290	3.7210	74.4200	-9.5058	2.9957
30	526.37	1.8998	3.6092	108.2760	-9.1308	3.4012
40	532.52	1.8779	3.5265	141.0600	-8.8663	3.6889

Table 2 Various parameters in linearization fitting (CP-*p*-appe)

$\beta/^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$	T_p/K	$(1/T_p)\times 10^{-3}$	$(1/T_p^2)\times 10^{-6}$	$(\beta/T_p^2)\times 10^{-6}$	$\ln(\beta/T_p^2)$	$\ln\beta$
5	503.51	1.9861	3.9446	19.7230	-10.8337	1.6094
10	517.29	1.9332	3.7373	37.3730	-10.1946	2.3026
20	522.96	1.9122	3.6565	73.1300	-9.5233	2.9957
30	532.57	1.8777	3.5258	105.7740	-9.1542	3.4012
40	540.46	1.8503	3.4236	136.9440	-8.8959	3.6889

Table 3 Various parameters in linearization fitting (P-*m*-appe)

$\beta/^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$	T_p/K	$(1/T_p)\times 10^{-3}$	$(1/T_p^2)\times 10^{-6}$	$(\beta/T_p^2)\times 10^{-6}$	$\ln(\beta/T_p^2)$	$\ln\beta$
5	502.65	1.9895	3.9581	19.7905	-10.8303	1.6094
10	509.01	1.9646	3.8597	38.5970	-10.1623	2.3026
20	521.54	1.9174	3.6764	73.5280	-9.5178	2.9957
30	529.47	1.8887	3.5672	107.0160	-9.1425	3.4012
40	536.11	1.8653	3.4793	139.1720	-8.8798	3.6889

Table 4 Various parameters in linearization fitting (CP-*m*-appe)

$\beta/^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$	T_p/K	$(1/T_p)\times 10^{-3}$	$(1/T_p^2)\times 10^{-6}$	$(\beta/T_p^2)\times 10^{-6}$	$\ln(\beta/T_p^2)$	$\ln\beta$
5	525.71	1.9022	3.6184	18.0918	-10.9201	1.6094
10	535.53	1.8673	3.4868	34.8680	-10.2639	2.3026
20	547.52	1.8264	3.3357	66.7140	-9.6151	2.9957
30	553.57	1.8065	3.2634	97.9020	-9.2315	3.4012
40	559.78	1.7864	3.1913	127.6520	-8.9662	3.6889

an unit in Kelvin, T, temperature in Kelvin.

The gel time of the four benzoxazines at different temperatures are shown in the Fig.11. Take $\ln(t_{gel})$ as the ordinate, $1/T$ as the abscissa (in Fig.12), the value of A and ΔE were figured out. And they are determined to be 1.78×10^{-12} , 7.99×10^{-12} , 2.15×10^{-11} and 9.80×10^{-14} , and 130, 124, 120, and 138 kJ/mol, respectively. The activation energy of the benzoxazines in gel process shows a similar trend in cross-linking. The introduction of the cyano group in P-*p*-appe decreases the activation energy of gelling, whereas the cyano group in P-*m*-appe has the activation energy of gelling increased.

Fig.11. Dependence of gel time upon temperature for four benzoxazines

Fig.12. Linearization fitting of the gelation behavior of the benzoxazines

4 Conclusions

Infrared spectroscopy has shown to be a wonderful method for the study of curing reaction of benzoxazines containing cyano and propargyl groups. The conversion of the propargyl group is higher than that of the cyano group during curing reaction. And the conversion of the cyano group of CP-*m*-appe is higher than that of CP-*p*-appe. The effect of introduction of cyano group in P-*m*-appe is more distinct than that in P-*p*-appe. The conversion of the propargyl in CP-*m*-appe is slower than that in P-*m*-appe. The apparent activation energies of the benzoxazines in curing were worked out through Kssinger and Ozawa fitting. The activation energies of the benzoxazines in gelling were also figured out. For Kssinger fitting, the E_a of four benzoxazines are 133, 126, 124 and 141 KJ/mol, respectively. The activation energies of the benzoxazines in curing and gelling display the same changes. The apparent activation energy of the benzoxazine with *meta*-propargyl group is lower than that with *para*-propargyl group. The cyano group makes the apparent activation energy of the benzoxazine with *para*-propargyloxy group decreased. And that the cyano group enhances the apparent activation energy of the benzoxazine with *meta*-propargyloxy group obviously.

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